

An Astrophysicist's Tale

Composed:
November 15th, 2020

Approximate Performance Time:
7:21

Composer:
Marcus A. Gordon (@magfoto)

Genre:
Electroacoustics / Live Coding

Instrumentation:
one drum synth, one polyphonic synthesizer, and
one hybrid synth

Performance:
<https://youtu.be/bZvPhnNOnyY>

Epigraph

An Astrophysicist's Tale is inspired by a dream of a young scientist, eager to explore the exoplanets that they will likely never see. The intent of the piece is to follow a journey through the process of terraforming a planet, so while listening, the composer wants you to imagine the creation of the fundamental wonders of our planet. Oceans forming from scattered droplets of magnetized water, forming of mists in the lower atmospheres, the overcast grey from clouds being slowly pierced by hues of blue and green, and earth tone colour palettes imbuing slowly growing forests.

The performance is of live coded music using an esoteric programming language as the writing mechanism for the score.

Composition

The composition is broken down into 2 major parts. The first, a speedy polyrhythm, with an emphasis on layers of beats. The second part slows the tempo down, while a new subtle structure is created in the background. This new structure unravels and exposes itself in the foreground as a texture filled with new polyrhythms combined with the old ones from the first part. The transformational method used in this piece is a gradual one, where the lead voice is swapped for a newer one....a higher pitched one. Listeners can interpret this change as a linear transition ($A \rightarrow B$) or an emergent one, which could still be perceived as linear, but with slight variations on the way from part 1 to part 2.

With its high energy opening, part 1 of this piece experiences its tail point 1:08 into the song, after which the slowdown in tempo occurs. Part 2 is finally created 2:18 into the song, yet still at this slower tempo. It isn't until about 4:00 that we hear the making of yet another layer, faster in speed, that gradually takes us back to a faster tempo we witnessed in part 1. It is within this window we witness the ins and outs of singular free playing notes, most quickly dissipating, while others eventually survive by transitioning into a musical chord.

The intent of the composer is for the listener to hear the formation of free floating notes into chords. The movement of work is reflective of the dynamic gathering of elements into structures, which then solidify into a collaborative arrangement of silence.

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